

O'RTA ASRLARDA OILA PEDAGOGIKASIGA OID FIKRLAR**Toshpo'latova Shaxnoza Shuhratovna**

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“Tarix va filologiya” kafedrası, Tarix fani o'qituvchisi.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Qur'oni Karim, hadisi Shariflarda oila va oilaviy munosabatlar va oilaviy tarbiyaga oid bir butun izchil qarashlar tizimi mavjud bo'lib, u o'z ichiga oilaning shakllanishi, rivojlanishi va mustaxkamlanishiga qaratilgan barcha jihatlarni qamrab oladi. Bu qarashlar ilohiyot nuqtai nazaridan o'rtacha qo'yilsada ular kishilarning turmush tarzlari, oilaviy munosabatlari talabidan kelib chiqqanligi uchun ham kundalik turmushga muvofiqligi haqida bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Qur'oni Karim, hadisi Sharif, Ibn Sinoning “Tadbiri al-manozil” nomli asari, “Avesto”, Muhammad ibn Muso al-Xorazmiy, Abu Nasr Farobiy, Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Abu Ali Ibn Sino, Muhammad qoshg'ariy, YUsof Xos Xojib, Kaykovus, Alisher Navoiy, Xusayn Voiz Koshifiy.

THOUGHTS ON FAMILY PEDAGOGY IN THE MIDDLE AGES

Abstract. In this article, there is a whole system of consistent views on family and family relations and family education in the Holy Qur'an, Hadith Sharifs, which includes all aspects aimed at the formation, development and strengthening of the family. If these views are averaged from theological point of view, it is stated that they are compatible with everyday life because they arise from the demands of people's lifestyles and family relationships.

Key words: Holy Qur'an, Hadith Sharif, Ibn Sina's work called "Tadbiri al-Manozil", "Avesta", Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorazmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Muhammad Qashg Ariy, Yusuf Khos Khajib, Kaikovus, Alisher Navoi, Husayn Vaiz Koshifi.

МЫСЛИ О СЕМЕЙНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКЕ В СРЕДНЕВЕКОВЬЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена система последовательных взглядов на семью и семейные отношения и семейное воспитание в Священном Коране, хадисах Шарифов, которая включает в себя все аспекты, направленные на формирование, развитие и укрепление семьи. Если эти взгляды усреднить с богословской точки зрения, то констатируется, что они совместимы с повседневной жизнью, поскольку вытекают из требований образа жизни людей и семейных отношений.

Ключевые слова: Священный Коран, Хадис Шариф, труд Ибн Сины «Тадбири аль-Манозиль», «Авеста», Мухаммад ибн Муса аль-Хоразми, Абу Наср Фараби, Абу Райхан

Беруни, Абу Али ибн Сина, Муҳаммад Кашир Арий, Юсуф Хос Хаджиб, Кайковус, Алишер Навои, Хусейн Байз Кошифи.

Eramizdan avvalgi 528-529 yillar orasida buyuk mutafakkir Zardusht tomonidan yaratilgan “Avesto” kitobida ham ta’lim-tarbiyaga, axloq-odobga oid qator g’oya va qarashlarni ko’rish mumkin. “Avesto”da ta’kidlanishicha, tarbiya hayotning tayanchi, shu boisdan har bir yoshni yaxshi o’qish va yozishga o’rgatish lozim. Uni yosh paytidanoq mehnat qilib, mehnatning tagi rohat ekanligini anglatish uchun daraxt ko’chati o’tkazishga, uy-ro’zg’or qurollari yasash, erga ishlov berish va chorva bilan shug’ullanishga o’rgatilishi shart. Zotan uning fikricha yaxshi va ezgu ishlar yaratish uchun kishi mehnat qilishi zarur, o’z qo’llari bilan moddiy noz-ne’matlar yaratmas ekan, u yashash lazzatini ham his qilmaydi, hayotning qadriga ham etmaydi.

U yuqoridagi fikrni davom ettirib, “Inson nafaqat mehnati tufayli o’zini va oilasini boqadi, balki unda erga va yurtga bo’lgan muhabbati ham paydo bo’ladi. Zotan har bir inson o’zi o’sibg’ulg’aygan zaminni, mamlakatni eng yaxshi va go’zal mamlakat deb tushunmog’i kerak”.

Uning bu fikrlaridan har bir inson faqat o’zining emas balki farzandlarini ham mehnatsevar qilib tarbiyalashi lozim. Chunki mehnatsevar bo’lmasdan turib, o’z erini, o’z Vatanini seva olmasligi tabiiy.

Islomda oilaviy tarbiyaning o’ziga xos xususiyatlari ham ko’rsatib o’tiladi. Bu xususiyatlar musulmonchilik talablaridan kelib chiqqan bo’lib, insonni ma’naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalash haqidaga umumiy g’oya bilan bog’liq. Musulmon oilalarida kuyov va kelinning avlod-ajdodlarining kelib chiqishini o’rganish, jismoniy va ma’naviy poklikga e’tibor berish an’anaga aylangan. Islomiy ma’naviyatda bolani oilada axloqiy tarbiyalash haqidagi qarashlar insoniylikga, ezgulikga va yaxshilikga da’vat etgan uchun ham umuminsoniy mazmunga egadir.

Shunga ko’ra, islom musulmonlariga xos bo’lgan diniy qadriyatgina bo’lib qolmasdan, balki umuminsoniy qadriyatdir. Milliy mustaqillik natijasida dinga va diniy qadriyatlarga bo’lgan munosabat tubdan o’zgardi va u oilada bolalarni axloqiy tarbiyalashning muhim omillaridan biriga aylanib, oilada tarbiyaviy ishlar samaradorligini oshirishga yordam bermoqda.

Sharq mutafakkirlarining ta’lim-tarbiya, oila va oilaviy tarbiya haqidagi qarashlari islom mafkurasi va uning qobig’ida shakllangan. Sharq mutafakkirlari ijodida aks etgan umuminsoniy g’oyalar islomiy ma’naviyat bilan hamohangdir.

Sharq mutafakkirlarining ilmiy merosida oila va oilada farzand tarbiyasi masalalariga katta e’tibor berganlar. Muhammad ibn Muso al-Xorazmiy, Abu Nasr Farobiy, Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Abu Ali Ibn Sino, Muhammad qoshg’ariy, YUsof Xos Xojib, Kaykovus, Alisher Navoiy, Xusayn

Voiz Koshifiy kabi mutafakkirlarning qator asarlarida bolalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalash masalalari o'rtaga qo'yilgan va ularni hal etish yo'llari ko'rsatib berilgan.

Oilada bola tarbiyasi masalasi Muhammad ibn Muso al-Xorazmiy qarashlarida ham mavjuddir. Uning aytishicha, "Ota-onalar ikki xil: tug'ilish otasi va ta'lim berish otasi: birinchisi jismoniy hayot sababli, ikkinchisi ruhiy hayot sababli". SHunga ko'ra ularni o'zviy birlikda olib qarash tarbiya ishida muhim ahamiyatga molikdir. Uning quyidagi so'zlar anchayin ibratlidir: "Zamondan yaxshiroq ta'lim beruvchi muallimni, insondan yaxshiroq talim oladigan o'quvchini ko'rmadim". Uning bu so'zlaridan bir tomondan ijtimoiy muhitni bola tarbiyasi uchun hal qiluvchi ta'sirini anglasak, ikkinchi tomondan inson shaxsi ta'lim natijasida kamolotga erishib borishi mumkinligini sezamiz.

Abu Rayxon Beruniy insonning axloqiy fazilatlarini, umuman axloqiy tushunchalarini insonning tabiati bilan bog'laydi. Inson tabiati esa avvalo oilada shakllanadi. Shunga ko'ra bola tarbiyasida ota-ona ta'siri va namunali benihoya kattadir. Masalan u ayollarga nasihat qilib, Abdulla ibn Jafar tilidan shunday deb yozadi: "Rashkdan saqlangin. U taloqning kalitidir.

Eringga tez-tez tanbeh qilishni senga ta'qiqalayman. Chunki tanbeh nafrat uyg'otadi. o'zingni bezab yurgin. Buning uchun yaxshi vosita surmadir. Yana xushbo'y atirlardan foydalaning. Ularning ichida eng yaxshisi suvdur". Uning bu fikrlari bevosita oilada farzand tarbiyasiga ta'luqlidir.

Beruniy tan va ruh pokligi masalasini ham o'rtaga tashlaydi. Beruniy ota-onalarga qarata bolaning mo'tadillikda saqlashni tavsiya etadi. Bunga asosan bolani qattiq g'azablanishdan, qo'rqish va hafalikdan, uy qusizlikdan saqlash orqali erishilishini aytib, ularni xohlagan va foydali narsasini topib berishga, sevmagan narsasidan uzoq lashtirishga harakat qilish kerakligini uqtiriladi. Ota-onaning bolaga turli munosabati turlicha xulqlarni keltirib chiqaradi.

Mutafakkir bola-xulq atvorining mo'tadilligi natijasida tan va ruh sog'lomligi kelib chiqishini ham ilmiy asoslab beradi. Beruniy bola tarbiyasida irsiyat muhit va tarbiya ta'sirini birdek muhim ekanligini ta'kidlab o'tgan edi. Beruniy axloqiy tarbiyaga musulmon dini talablaridan kelib chiqqan holda yondoshadi. Axloqiylik yaxshilik va yomonlik o'rtasidagi kurash natijasida namoyon bo'ladi va shakllanadi. Uning bu fikri o'z davri uchun yangi va ilmiy bashorat edi.

Oila va oilada bola tarbiyasi masalasi Abu Ali Ibn Sinoning ilmiy merosida ham muhim o'rin egallaydi. U o'zining qator asarlarida bolaning salomatligi, uning tarbiyasi haqida, eng muhimi bola ruhiyatini o'rganish borasida ko'plab qimmatbaho fikrlarni yozadi. Ularning hammasi bir butun bo'lib, muayyan pedagogik qarashlar tizimini tashkil etadi va u ma'naviy-axloqiy barkamol insonni shakllantirish haqidagi g'oyaga borib taqaladi. Ibn Sinoning "Tadbiri

al-manozil” nomli asarida katta bir bob oila va oilaviy tarbiya masalalariga bag‘ishlangandir.

Ibn Sino oilada bola tarbiyasi ancha murakkab va nozik bo‘lib, uni bolaning yoshligidan boshlab va izchillik bilan olib borish lozimligini uqtiradi. U ona allasining tarbiyaviy ahamiyati ha qida to‘xtalib, “Alla” ikki vazifani bajaradi, deydi. Birinchisi, uni tebratish or qali bolaga jismoniy orom bag‘ishlanadi; ikkinchisi, beshikni bir maromda tebratishdan onaning mehri jo‘sh uradi, bolasiga bo‘lgan muhabbatidan onaning orzu umidi yurak to‘ridan sil q ib chiqadi. Bu o‘ziga xos qo‘shi q bolasi uchun qasidadek yangraydi va u farzandining murg‘ak qalbiga singib boradi. SHu tarzda bolada o‘zi ham anglolmagan xolat paydo bo‘ladi. U asta-sekin bu yorug‘ olamni anglay boshlaydi. Ana shu anglashdan o‘rganish boshlanadi. Xuddi shu o‘rganish tarbiyalanishdir. Zotan o‘rganish sezishdan kelib chi qadi. Ibn Sino ana shu xolatga e‘tiborini qaratib, “YOsh bolaning sezgirlik quvvati katta odamga teng keladi”, degan fikrni bildiradi.

Ibn Sino bola tarbiyasida oila boshlig‘i otaning roliga alohida e‘tibor beradi. “Agar oilada – deydi u, oila boshlig‘i tajribasizlik, no‘noqlik qilsa u oila a‘zolarini yaxshi tarbiyalay olmaydi va og‘ibatda bundan yomon natijalar kelib chi q ishi mumkin”. Bola yaxshi yo‘lga qo‘yilsa, oila baxtli bo‘ladi. Oilaning eng muhim vazifasi bola tarbiyasi hisoblanadi. Ota-ona kim bo‘lishidan qat‘iy nazar, bu vazifani ma’suliyat bilan ado etishi lozim. Ibn Sino “tadbiri al-manozil” asarida er va xotinning yaxshi sifatlarini sanab o‘tadi. Ularning shaxsiy namunalari bola uchun o‘rnak bo‘lib, kelajak ta qdirini belgilashda muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligi alohida u qtiriladi.

Ibn Sino oilada bolani ma’naviy – axloqiy tarbiyalashda mehnatsevarlikning roliga alohida urg‘u berib, ota-onalarni farzandlariga nisbatan kasb-xunar o‘rgatishga chaqiradi. Mehnatni ulug‘laydi. Mehnatsiz hayot kechirishning bolaga bo‘lgan salbiy ta’sirini ko‘rsatib beradi.

XI asrda yashab ijod etgan mutafakkir Yusuf Xos hojib o‘zining “ qutadg‘u bilig”da bola tarbiyasi ha q ida to‘xtalib, shunday yozadi: “Farzand qanchalik bilimli, a qlli-xushli bo‘lsa ota-onasining yuzi shunchalik yorug‘ bo‘ladi”. U bola tarbiyasida otaning ma’suliyatiga alohida e‘tibor beradi. “Kimning o‘g‘il-qizi erka bo‘lsa, deb yozadi u unga shu kishining o‘zi mungli bo‘lib yig‘laydi. Ota bolani kichikligida bebosh qilib qo‘ysa bolada gunoh yo‘q barcha jaf o taning o‘zida; o‘g‘il- qizning xulq -atvori yaramas bo‘lsa, bu yaramas ishni ota q ilgan bo‘ladi.

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